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‘SEBA’ IN PURI TEMPLE AND THE BALANCE OF POWER : THE CASE OF GAJAPATIS AND GADAJAT KINGS

Thobir Kumar Lima

The formation of the state of Odisha has been the resultant outcome of a long history of complex coalescing and integration of local, divisional, subregional elements into a distinctive region. The regional dynamics is therefore constituted by economic, political, religious, and cultural forces operating at the local and subregional levels. In early medieval Odisha, there had been a number of smaller cultural-political-territorial zones named as Kalinga (south of Chilika upto northern Andhra, Utkala (coastal Odisha, broadly north of Chilika upto Midnapur area), Kosala (parts of present day Bolangir and Sambalpur). In central Odisha’s hill and jungle tract, in the upland plain and highlights of the mountainous regions of Odisha there existed local rajas who were ruling in various mandalas, such as Airavarta Mandala, Yamagartta Mandala (central Odisha), Bonai Mandala (Sundargarh), Khijjinga Mandala (Mayurbhanj and Keonjhar) and Khinjali Mandala (Phulbani and some part of undivided Ganjam’s eastern ghat area). The process of formation of the region of Odisha by integrating these territorial units into one Utkala or Odisha in the Somavamsi, Ganga and Gajapati period (from 10th century to 16th century C.E.) is marked by complex web of dynamic policies between the unified centre of the Gangas and Gajapatis on the one hand and the feudatory ‘peripheries’ on the other. Such negotiations and contestations between the centre and peripheries in 16th to 18th centuries is the subject of the present paper. The paper explores the dynamic relations between the Gajapatis of Puri on the one hand and

feudatories of the peripheries of Odisha on the other. Such negotiations and contestation were deeply political in nature but this political relation expressed itself not in political term but through cultural politics of privileges and access to the regional Cult centre of Jagannatha at Puri. This contestation and negotiations between the Gajapati kingship and feudal rajas resulted in the expansion of creations of many centres of Jagannatha temples in feudatory states between 17th and 19th centuries. These constructions of big Jagannatha temples in peripheral feudatory states of Odisha need to be located in the context of this dynamic relation between the Gajapati Centre and Feudatory states of Odisha, known as Gadajats. The paper also explores the ritual privileges and access rights to Jagannatha temple accorded by Khurda Gajapatis to feudatory states in 17th and 18th century. The Gajapatis were desperate to retrieve their endangered political status and the rising power of the feudatory states. In this paper, I do a reading of the royal letters of the Gajapatis to show that the ritual diplomacy of privileges and access to Jagannatha temple is used as a tool to recentre the pre-eminence of Khurda Gajapati, a pre-eminence which had already been lost and had given way to many centres in the realms of the Gadajatas of Odisha.

In the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, there was a marked expansion in the number of feudatory states in Odisha. In 1592, only a handful of states were recognised as independent principalities by Akbar. These included Khurda, Keonjhar, Hariharpur (Mayurbhanj), Aul and Sarangagarh.¹ However, we do know that there were a number of feudatory chiefs at the time of Kapilendradeva who had voiced their resentment against his authority, and were accordingly chastised.² These states, such as Ranpur, Kujang, Kanika, Dompura, Khallikot and others were linked to the

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- 1 Kulke, Hermann 'Jagannatha as State Deity under the Gajapatis of Orissa' in Eschmannn. A Cult of Jagannatha and the Regional Tradition of Orissa. p. 208
 - 2 Jaya vijaya dwara inscription, Jagannatha temple, Puri.

temple and the Gajapati both territorially and ideologically. The military account of Khan-i-Dauran (1660-1663) lists a number of ‘zamindars’ and ‘killadars’ of Ranpur, Kaluapada, Banki and others³ who fought the Mughal armies on behalf of the Khurda raja. This indicates that certain surrounding principalities were under the dominant influence of Khurda, both through the temple-Gajapati link as well as independently as military vassals. The intricate web of the links of obligation that connected the Gajapati with the Gadajata rajas were expressed through a combination of military, ritual and economic terms. Indeed, it is difficult to separate and define the diverse motivations that underlay this interaction.

A statement from the Ranapur Rajavamsavali recording the resolution of military conflict in ritual terms illustrates these linkages —‘The Maharaja of Puri had a battle with the Nawab and Jagannatha Patnaik of Ranapur helped the Maharaja of Tapanga Gada. So the Gajapati Maharaja ordered to honour the Raja Narendra Mahapatra of Ranapur with the presentation of white umbrella and bugle.⁴ The ritual gift of the umbrella and bugle, both symbols of royal sovereignty by the Gajapati, marked an acknowledgement of the Ranapur raja's support and of his status as independent ruler. The state of Ranapur was within the sphere of influence of the Khurda-Puri complex, both by virtue of territorial proximity as well as ideological and military linkages. The Ranapur rajas were offered a large number of special privileges in the temple during their annual pilgrimage; these were conferred by the Gajapati as a mark of favour. The increased status of the feudatory raja, in this case, his ritual status in the temple, reflected the greatness of his overlord, hence it was in the interest of the Gajapati, as well as that of the Ranapur raja, to mutually honour each other.

3 Sarkar, Jadunath ‘The History of Orissa in seventeenth century Reconstructed from Persian Sources’, p. 162.

4 ‘Genealogy of the Royal Family of Ranapur ’, ORP. Ms. 867 Sanad, p.28.

In another instance, the Rajavamsavali of Khallikota recounts the appointment of its founder, a Bhuiyan-Khandait (landowner) by origin, to being appointed feudatory chief by Gajapati Purusottamadeva during the Kanci-Kaberi campaign.⁵ The state of Keonjhar is described as having been a gift from the Gajapati to his son-in-law, a Rajput prince.⁶ The dynamism of the feudatory-Gajapati relationship was kept alive through ritualised economic relationships in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, especially through the redistributive system of the temple. The socio-economic and revenue networks of the feudatory states were mobilised within the temple sphere, and these links were sanctioned by, and channelised through the Khurda Raja.

The *Chhamu Chitau*, or the royal proclamations of the Gajapati, issued primarily in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, is vibrantly illustrative of this ritual mobilisation of goods and services. The archival material of *Madala Panji* which the first Odishan Research Project procured from temple scribe (*deuli karana*) of the Jagannatha temple in 1971 contains about 160 chhamu-chitaus, most of them being addressed to altogether 32 rajas, princes and zamindars during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries: Ranapur, Athagarh, Khandapada, Dhenkanal, Tigiria, Nayagarh, Baramba, Banapur, Khallikote, Sambalpur, Tekkali, Sukinda, Jeypore, Paralakhemundi, Vijayanagar, Khemundi, Banki, Boudh, Kujang, Madhupur, Mayurbhanj, Parikud and Sonapur.⁷

One of the early letters issued by raja Mukundadeva in 1662 CE illustrates the peculiar Chhamu Chitau Policy of Khurda rajas.

5 'Khallikota Zamindar ', Local Records Vol. 59 , ORP, GOMLM, Mss. 423, p.1

6 K. Misra, Kendujhar, translated by P. C. Mishra. 1932, ORP, Mss. 552, p.5.

7 Madala Panji

*“Raja Nilakantha Deva of Badakhimedi in south Orissa has gone to Puri for darsan of Jagannatha. We sent Paramananda Pattanaik along with him. He will stay with him and help him perform the darsan. The palanquin, the royal umbrella, a fan made of peacock feathers and the sword and dagger of the raja will be kept at a place near the Lion’s gate. You will be allowed to take his big fan and other necessary articles of prestige. After being carried over the seven steps of the batadvara of the jagamohana, all this will be kept at the Jayavijaya dvara inside the temple compound. He will worship at the Jayavijaya dvara. Entering the sanctum sanctorum, he will have darsan. Then he will perform the golden chamara seba. After this he will come through the inner southern gate and after having had darsan of the side deities, he will go out through the Lion’s gate”.*⁸

For instance, a letter issued by Virakesarideva in 1749 to the temple parichhas, pertaining to the privileges of the Ranapur rajas, runs as follows-

*“On the 22nd day of (the month of) Mesa in the 7th anka of this king a written order of the king was issued. You should give sadi and mahaprasad from the temple to the king (Narendra) of Ranapur in the traditional manner for supplying ropes (simuli)”*⁹.

Another letter issued by the same ruler in 1750 requests the Dhenkanal raja to supply iron for building the rathas and bestows the usual honour of *sadi* and *chandana* in return.¹⁰ Owing to a more tenuous political status of the Gajapati and greater independence of the feudatory states in the eighteenth century, what was previously simply requisitioned, even for temple functions, now had to be requested. These links of supply and

8 Chhamu Chitau

9 ibid

10 ibid

demand were restructured within a changed political milieu, wherein the Khurda raja was negotiating his status as Gajapati while attempting to achieve a balance with the pressures exerted by higher military authorities, the Mughals and the Nawabs. The Gajapati's ritual link with the temple, however, was a powerful one, and his ability to legitimise the feudatory rajas within the temple network accorded him a unique authority. As has been shown elsewhere in greater detail,¹¹ the Khurda raja had a wide range of different ritual privileges at his disposal, which they granted according to their position of their princely recipient, their loyalty and support the Khurda raja received or expected from them.

The seventeenth and eighteenth centuries saw a curious interplay of political trends in the region, wherein cultural factors played as significant a role in state formation as military strategy. The Khurda raja achieved the status of Gajapati through shrewd foresight and military superiority as much as it was conferred upon him by the Mughal emperor. Thus, while he was militarily subordinate to Delhi, he was ideologically superior, even dominant in the region. On the other hand, his status of supremacy depended largely on his relationships with the feudatory rajas. While they upheld his ritual dominance, as the status of their own lineages was linked to the superior position of the Gajapati, the increased circumscription of his temporal power began to limit the exercise of his authority to the temple sphere. In the twelfth anka year of Sri Virakesari Maharaja and in the fourteenth day of Mithuna, a letter of privilege was written by the Maharaja as follows:

“Let this be known to the Pariksa and all the concerned officers of the Bada Deula from this letter that Shakira Sricandana of Banki will

11 Kulke, Hermann 'Ksetra and Ksatra' in *Kings and Cults: State Formation and Legitimation in India and Southeast Asia*, Manohar Publications, New Delhi. 1993, p. 51-65.

accomplish darsana of the Gods. So, on our behalf, he should be given all due honours according to convention. In the former days the Srichandanas of Banki were appointed Pariksa. So he should be supplied with a silk fan for his fanning service.... The bhoga prasada should be supplied to him in a similar way as the Pariksa of the Temple enjoys the honours.....”¹²

This Chhamu Chitau issued by Virakesarideva in the mid-eighteenth century illustrates the manner in which feudatory chiefs were accorded a privileged status in the temple realm, through the performance of a *seba*, a ritual service. The fact that this event was announced and validated by the Gajapati, indicates his status of primacy in the temple sphere and the predominance of his right over temple functions. A closer analysis of these processes will clarify the situation. The reign of Virakesarideva, who succeeded his father Ramachandradeva after a struggle (which has been discussed earlier in the chapter), was characterised by a proliferation of Chhamu Chitau. Kulke views this as a consequence of Virakesari's efforts to mobilise material resources as well as re-establish his diminished authority over the Gadajata rajas, which he did through his link with the temple.¹³ Temple *seba* was a privileged share in the process of worship: they were honours that constituted authority in the temple realm. In a broad sense, the status inherent in the notion of *seba* lay in the degree of access to the deity that it afforded. Moreover, temple honours publicly affirmed the individual's involvement in the temple's redistributive system, access to which was synonymous with a kind of ritual authority in society.

12 Chhamu Chitau, in Jagannatha Sthala vrttantam, ORP Ms. 441 p. 94

13 Kulke, Hermann 'Ksetra and Ksatra' in Kings and Cults: State Formation and Legitimation in India and Southeast Asia, Manohar Publications, New Delhi. 1993, p. 51-65.

The raja had been intimately connected to the temple since Ganga Anangabhima declared himself to be the rauta (deputy) of Jagannatha in the thirteenth century.¹⁴ The raja's links with the temple had been further strengthened by the Gajapatis, particularly by Purusottamadeva, who established the tradition of *chhera pahara* (ritual sweeping), the raja's exclusive seba, as an essential part of temple ritual. In the eighteenth century, the Bhoi rajas of Khurda were struggling to retain their position of primacy among the Gadajata rajas of the region. In this context, the raja's ritual status as Gajapati, the Adyasebaka, recipient of the first bhoga in any ceremony, symbolising his predominance in the temple's material and status networks, was central to the maintenance of his position. By conferring temple privileges upon the Gadajata chiefs, the raja mobilised material resources via the temple's ritual networks. For instance, the raja of Daspalla was given the privilege of providing wood for the rathas during the annual car festival, while iron and ropes came from Dhenkanal, Talcher and Ranapur. What had possibly been requisitioned earlier was now concretised into a ritual exchange, sealed with the sadi and sandalwood, symbols of privileged status in the temple. The raja of Banki was allowed *darsana* at night, an exclusive privilege of the Gajapati. He was also appointed pariksa (*pariccha*, a high-ranking temple official), being accorded honours due to the highest temple official. He was allowed to perform *chamara seba* or fanning service and was provided with a silk fan with a golden handle as symbol of that honour. Service was considered to be a great privilege, as it implied a direct participation in the daily routine activity of the deity and thus a greater proximity to the deity. The Gajapati himself performed *chhera pahara* (sweeping of the chariots of the lords during the annual rathayatra by Gajapati at the time of Purushottamadeva Gajapati in early 16th century) at each ratha jatra, a privilege that reaffirmed his direct link with the deity before thousands

14 'Puri Inscription of the year 1237 A.D' in Epigraphia Indica 30, 1954, p. 202.

of devotees. By formally honouring their service, the Gajapati was allowing the feudatories a share in his own niche in the redistributive system. It also reinforced his position of primacy in that system. This point is beautifully illustrated in a manuscript of the former *rajguru* of Keonjhar: It describes the manner in which the raja of Keonjhar mobilised the tribal hinterlands of his own capital in exactly the same way as the Khurda raja engaged the feudatory chiefs in the service of Jagannatha. Keonjhar had its own Jagannatha temple along with the annual ratha jatra celebration. The raja placed on the Bhuiyans and Juangs, semi-tribal landed groups belonging to that area, the responsibility of preparing the ropes for pulling the chariots. On the day itself they came with their ropes shouting 'Hari Bola' before tying them to the chariot wheels. For this service, they were awarded a *sadi* and an honourarium from the temple. They were also asked to pay a tax in kind called *paluka* on lands that were previously rent-free. The imposition of a material obligation affirmed their involvement in the dominant redistributive network. The ritual nature of their mobilisation subsumed the material obligation that they were placed under. The Gajapati had held this position of honour for the region since early medieval times, but each raja had this privilege within his own domain. Ganga ruler Anangabhima's declaration that his kingdom was the 'empire of Jagannatha' (Jagannatha samrajya) confirmed the raja's absolute control over his land. As the *rauta* (deputy) of the predominant deity of the region, the raja had assumed a level of authority that had the sanction of divine power, its ritual nature being more effective in the case of a rebellion than mere military supremacy.

In conclusion, the notion of temple seba indicated privileged access to the deity. Yet, underlying the ritualised distribution of these services by the Khurda raja in the eighteenth century showed a desperate attempt on the part of Khurda Gajapati to retrieve his irretrievable status which had been diminished in the eyes of feudatory states on account of defeat in the hands of Moghuls and the marriage of Gajapati to a muslim girl. The imposition of

ritual obligations on feudatory states was an attempt to limit their resistance to the Gajapati King. In the end, the feudatory states created their own centres of power by replicating the architectonic of Puri Temple city in their respective capital cities. This resulted in the construction of magnificent temples in feudatory states of Keonjhar, Mayurbhan, Nilagiri, Khallikote, and in almost all other feudatory states of Odisha.

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